

**THE EFFECT ANALYSIS OF MOTIVATION, COMPETENCE AND
ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE
OF JAKARTA SOCIAL DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT

All this time, government institutions are still overshadowed by stigma, the poor performance of civil servants. Therefore, this research was conducted to analyze the influence of performance factors, including motivation, competence and organizational culture. This study uses a quantitative approach, causal associative research methods, descriptive and inferential analysis. The total population is 50 respondents, the sample technique used in the census and the analysis method uses multiple linear regression. The results of the analysis show that motivation, competence and organizational culture both partially and simultaneously have a significant effect on performance.

Keywords : Motivation, Competence, Organizational Culture, Performance

PROEM

In order to achieve national goals as stated in paragraph 4 of the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (the 1945 Constitution), namely building a democratic, just and prosperous country. Then it is needed the State Civil Service (ASN) or Civil Servants (PNS) who are professionally free of political intervention, clean from the practices of corruption, collusion and nepotism, capable of holding public services that are transparent, accountable and credible. So that it can play a role as the glue of unity and brotherhood based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution.

Development will be achieved successfully, in accordance with the wishes if the servants of the state work seriously, so that they have an efficient, effective and optimal

performance. State apparatus in this case Civil Servants (PNS) who have good performance will have a positive impact on development outcomes. In addition, its existence will bring change towards competitive and characterized country.

One effort to get effective civil servant performance is very important to be implemented in every government agency. Bureaucratic reform is a repetitive improvement which is an element of non-physical development, especially development in the field of administration which involves the work process of civil servants in government agencies. If it is observed now, the accuracy and objectives of work activities become problems that need to be immediately integrated, synchronized, coordinated and adjusted between units with each other. Hopefully, these efforts can improve the performance of civil servants. Friendly in service, fast in work, honest, responsible and not taking bribes. In addition, employees also prioritize professional attitudes. Regular work attitude, obeying the rules, upholding values, etc.

In line with the explanation above, Jakarta Social Service always strives to provide good management and service governance. This is done, as a form of synchronization of good governance, between the central and regional governments. Through improving bureaucracy, improving the quality of ASN / PNS, including through the provision of learning assignments to higher education levels (S2 and S3), regional performance benefits and other incentives. However, Jakarta Social Service also realizes that building HR takes quite a long time, therefore in the process many face dynamics. Such as limited budget, difficulty in directing old employees, difficulty in improving the bribery culture and others.

The main dynamic is that the performance of employees gets complaints from the public, especially the social care families. Still found employees who are less friendly and polite in providing services to the assisted citizens, being arrogant towards the families of the assisted citizens, and so on. This condition adds to the poor image of social services in the eyes of the public, especially DKI Jakarta.

Based on confirmation by several employees, the above problem is true. Employees do not address the above problems, but one thing must be understood is that taking care of social care residents is not as simple as managing goods or objects. It takes a lot of energy, time, thoughts, emotions, etc., so that employees are often easily fatigued. At the same time, there were families of the inmates coming, but also their

treatment did not understand the conditions, as if everything was going easily. With fatigued conditions, making emotions rise or ignore visitor requests.

Nevertheless, the social service employees realized that it was all their duty, but as humans they had their limits. Therefore, it needs encouragement (motivation) from various parties, especially from the head of the social service. Then the importance of being given training and education that is relevant to the work, so that employee competence in terms of taking care of the inmates is maximized, namely the employees become intelligently intellectual, emotional and spiritual. In addition, humility and mutual cooperation among employees is a good culture to strengthen each other.

Based on the above phenomenon, this research was conducted to find out about the Influence of Motivation, Competence and Organizational Culture on Employees Performance of Social Department in Jakarta.

THEORETIC

Management

Management is the organization or governance of the organization. So, all types of good organizational management include planning, organizing, implementing and controlling are forms of management activities, (Hasibuan, 2013). Including making efforts to motivate employees by providing compensation, so that the implementation of the task goes well, is part of the management function. This confirms, that management has a broad meaning. Its scope covers all aspects that exist within and outside the organization.

Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management in the simplest sense means managing employees. In each organization there will be a department or department that focuses on handling HR, from recruitment to appointment, commonly called HR department or personnel. The HRD or Personnel Department has the duty to ensure that each employee works based on their respective competencies, ensuring that each position or position is filled by the right person, maintaining employees or employees by providing training and education and developing HR through career paths. In organizations, HRM specifically regulates employees. As for what is regulated includes behavior, work and development.

Motivation

Simply, motivation can be interpreted as encouraging work morale. The spirit of work can be born from within, this is triggered by goals, expectations and individual characteristics. While the spirit of the external form of support both coming from the family for example in the form of morale (advice and prayer), support from coworkers for example in the form of helping help, support from the leadership for example in the form of supervision and support in the form of compensation. These various supports become the source of the birth of work motivation for employees.

The results of research conducted by Harras (2018), Mathodah (2018), Dinantara (2018), Murty (2012), and Riyadi (2011) suggest that bringing a sense of enthusiasm in work will produce a good job (performance). in other words, statistically motivation proved to have an effect on performance

Competence

In a simple sense, competence is the ability to work. In practice, capabilities have different applications, the amount depends on the portion needed. In work at the operational level the portion of skills is more dominant, but on the contrary in jobs at the level of directors or professionals the portion of knowledge is more dominant. Competence depends on the level of needs (type of work and position). This, shows if competence has a very large influence on the quality of implementation and work results (performance).

Explanation above. reinforced by the results of research conducted by Sriwidodo and Haryanto (2010), Safwan and Abdullah (2014), Widyatmini and Hakim (2011), Manik and Syafrina (2018), and Posuma (2013) suggest that competence has a significant effect on performance.

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is understood as organizational values that become a habit at work. For example being friendly to coworkers, being alert to helping colleagues, being enthusiastic in every job, being obedient to company rules and policies, and so forth. Embedded values in each job directly affect the pleasure and pride of employees because they can do the best work. In the future, organizational culture has become a strength of identity. Each member competes to be the best in goodness.

The results of research conducted by Arianty (2015), Satyawati and Suartana (2014), and Arianto (2013) suggest that organizational culture has a significant effect on performance. In detail, it is explained that the quality of work depends on the embedded values and mood of employees. If the emotional state is stable and the support of a high work environment will have an influence on the implementation of quality work.

Performance

Performance can be understood as a series of work, consisting of processes and work results, as well as fulfilling assumptions of quality and quantity. Because performance is work and work results, it can be ascertained the most important thing in the organization or company. Employee performance is believed to be an indicator of organizational success. If a work process is carried out effectively it will produce an efficient work, and that is why companies get many benefits. Therefore, in order to improve the performance of employees, the DKI Jakarta Social Service encourages the development of human resources both in terms of competence and personality. Many research results suggest that the main relationship between employees and organizations is performance. Therefore, many companies are willing to do anything to improve the performance of their employees.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach and causal associative research methods. The method of answering the problem formulation uses inferential analysis with the type of descriptive discussion. Furthermore, this study uses the method of multiple linear regression analysis. The aim is to explain the aspects that are appropriate or relevant to the observed phenomena and explain the characteristics of the phenomena or problems.

The sampling technique used in the study was the technique of census samples or saturated samples. Where the entire population is used as a sample in the study, due to the limitations of the existing population or research want to make general results with a small error. The number of analysis units that were sampled were 50 employees of the DKI Jakarta Social Service in the Parmadi Khusnul Khotimah Social Rehabilitation Institution.

In an effort to collect data, the research instrument was made in the form of a questionnaire with closed statement types and measuring instruments using a Likert Scale. In the Likert Scale 5 respondents were given choices to find out their attitudes, opinions and responses to the questionable situation. Then the data is recapitulated and processed using SPSS for Windows Software.

RESULT

Validity Test

Validity shows the extent to which a measuring instrument is able to measure what it wants to measure. The measurement of validity test is done, if the positive correlation coefficient and > 0.3 then the relevant indicator is considered valid. The questionnaire was divided into four main factors, namely motivation (X1) with 10 items of statements, competencies (X2) with 10 items of statements, organizational culture (X3) with 10 items of statements and performance (Y) with 10 statements. So, the number of statements in the questionnaire is 40 items with a total of 50 respondents.

Based on the validity table above, shows all the items in the statement in this study have a Pearson Correlation value greater than 0.3 and also have a significantly smaller value than the standard required < 0.05 . It can be concluded that the items in this study have a Pearson Correlation value greater than 0.3 and also have a significantly smaller value than the standard required < 0.05 . It can be concluded that the questions used to measure motivation variables (X1), competence (X2), organizational culture (X3) and performance (Y) are valid. For this reason, these items can be used in regression testing.

Reliability Test

Reliability test is used to find out whether the indicator or questionnaire used is reliable or reliable as a variable measuring instrument. The reliability of an indicator or questionnaire can be seen from the cronbach value, s alpha (α), that is if the cronbach value, s alpha (α) is greater ($>$) 0.60 then the indicator or questionnaire is reliable, whereas if the value is cronbach, s alpha (α) smaller ($<$) 0.60 then the indicator or questionnaire is not reliable. following below, the results of reliability test data are presented.

Table 1. Reliability Test

Variable	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Standar Reliabilitas</i>	Information
Motivation	0.727	0,60	Reliabel
Competence	0.784	0,60	Reliabel
Organizational culture	0.831	0,60	Reliabel
Performance	0.860	0,60	Reliabel

Source: Research data, 2018

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that all statements are reliable. This can be seen from the value of Cronbach's Alpha which is much greater than the Reliable level > 0.60. In other words, all statements in this study have a good level of reliability and can be used in the analysis in this study.

Partial Test

Table 2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.190	2.496		2.480	.015
	Motivation	.255	.111	.252	2.295	.024
	Competence	.168	.137	.134	2.104	.037
	Organizational culture	.577	.096	.614	6.027	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Research data, 2018

Based on the results of the data above, it can be stated the following explanation and analysis of the research:

1. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance by 0.255. This means that if the employee brings enthusiasm in every job, it will produce good work. In other words, the results of this analysis confirm that performance is closely related to motivation in order to encourage its members to behave as expected.
2. Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance by 0.168. This explains, competence is interpreted as a fundamental attitude towards self that is emitted in work in order to produce maximum work. In other words, competence is the awareness of someone to work in total, strive for the best, and

believe in all their abilities. The manifestation of all that is, totality in work, professional, thorough, and so forth.

3. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at 0.577. The results of this study have an explanation, embedded organizational values in each activity, giving a high influence on employee performance. This happens, because culture can make the emotional state of employees more stable, so that employees can work more focused and produce appropriate work.

Simultaneous Test

Table 3. Simultaneous Test

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3558.539	3	1186.180	137.654	.000 ^a
	Residual	939.266	109	8.617		
	Total	4497.805	112			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, Competence, Organizational culture						
b. Dependent Variable: Performance						

Source: Research data, 2018

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.889 ^a	.791	.785	2.545
a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, Competence, Organizational culture				

Source: Research data, 2018

Based on the table above, it explains that the variables of motivation, competence and organizational culture together have a positive and significant effect on performance with a contribution value of 0.785. This finding confirms that in carrying out work, work morale is very important to ensure that every job is done well. In addition, the level of work ability of employees is very important to the results of work and the quality of work, whether the work really is in accordance with the SOP. In addition, the existence of an organizational culture makes the work atmosphere conducive, so that the implementation of work can be carried out optimally.

Based on the analysis and discussion above, the research findings can be presented as follows:

1. Both partially and simultaneously the motivation, competence and organizational culture have a significant effect on performance. This is a reminder for the organization to ensure that all three factors exist and become part of the organization.
2. Organizational culture is statistically the dominant factor in performance. This is a reminder for organizations to make organizational values as basis of work.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, in the previous chapter, conclusions can be taken as follows:

1. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
2. Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
3. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
4. Motivation, competence and organizational culture simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

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